

A LIGHTWEIGHT HYBRID MOBILENETV2– LIGHTGBM MODEL FOR TRAFFIC SIGNAL CLASSIFICATION IN RESOURCE- CONSTRAINED SYSTEMS

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Abstract—Traffic light recognition is an essential part of how self-driving cars and smart city systems work, which ensure road safety. While deep learning models like YOLOv5 are really accurate, they often come with high computational cost and tend to be slow in resource constrained devices. This paper introduces a hybrid classification model that combines MobileNetV2 feature extraction capabilities and LightGBM for detection and classification. The model is trained on a curated dataset of cropped traffic light images, preprocessed to remove noise from surrounding elements such as buildings, vehicles, and pedestrians. Color histogram attributes were added to enhance its performance. The model achieves an impressive classification accuracy of 97%, demonstrating superior performance while maintaining computational efficiency.

Keywords—Traffic Light Recognition, MobileNetV2, LightGBM, Hybrid Model, Transfer Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recent research has focused on developing efficient systems for traffic signal detection, recognition and classification, which are essential for autonomous vehicles and smart cities. Deep learning approaches, like convolutional neural networks (CNN) and You Only Look Once (YOLO) variants, have shown promising results in accurately detecting and classifying traffic signals in real-time [7].

However, traditional and well-known often suffer from large parameters and high computational costs, limiting their integration into resource-constrained environments [3].

Recent studies have highlighted the demand for lighter, more efficient options. [5] pointed out the operational challenges of YOLOv5, mentioning its heavy resource use as a barrier to broader application. To address these challenges, this study introduces a hybrid model that combines MobileNetV2, a lightweight convolutional neural network pre-trained on ImageNet for feature extraction, with Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM), a fast, gradient boosting framework, for signal classification. MobileNetV2 is recognized for its efficiency and lower

parameter count, while LightGBM offers quick training and minimal memory use [2].

The main goal of this research is to create a lightweight yet highly accurate traffic signal classification system capable of detecting red, yellow, and green signals. The model is trained on a dataset of cropped and noise-reduced traffic signal images, where “noise-reduced” refers to removing non-signal objects such as vehicles, roads, trees, and other background objects. It is further improved by adding color histogram features to boost classification performance.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 1 presents the research background and motivation. Section 2 reviews related literature. Section 3 explains the methodology, including dataset preprocessing, model architecture, and training procedures. Section 4 shares the experimental results and performance evaluation. Finally, Section 5 concludes the study and suggests directions for future work.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

[12] introduced the DeepTLR system, a deep learning framework for real-time traffic light detection and classification. Their single convolutional neural network processed raw image pixels without needing prior location knowledge. It employed bounding box regression after classifying pixel regions and achieved a recall of 91.4% and a precision of 95.6% at a resolution of 1280x960. The system supported real-time performance, reaching up to 33 Frame Per Seconds (FPS) on standard-resolution inputs, making it suitable for autonomous driving systems.

[11] proposed a lightweight algorithm based on YOLOv4-Tiny for traffic sign detection. They focused on optimizing anchor box generation using a refined K-means clustering technique designed for the traffic sign dataset. Evaluated on the TT100K dataset, the model yielded a mAP@0.5 of 52.07%. The results indicated improved recall and localization precision, showing the algorithm’s effectiveness in real-time situations.

[4] looked at the efficiency of LightGBM in memory-constrained environments. They noted that LightGBM’s low memory consumption results from its histogram-based

algorithm, which organizes continuous feature values into bins. This method removes the need to store all data points in memory during each tree split, making it more efficient than traditional algorithms that require pre-sorting every data point.

[14] conducted an empirical evaluation of YOLOv5 compared to SSD for traffic sign recognition. Their dataset contained 2,182 images across eight classes and was augmented for generalization. YOLOv5 achieved a mean average precision (mAP) of 97.70%, with every individual class recording mAPs above 90%. In contrast, SSD trailed with an overall accuracy of 90.14%, and recognition of underrepresented classes dropped to 78.32%. Additionally, YOLOv5 notably exceeded SSD in processing speed, handling 30 FPS as opposed to SSD's 3.49 FPS. These findings confirmed YOLOv5's suitability for real-time applications.

[5] conducted a comparative study of YOLOv5 and SSD MobileNet for traffic signal detection tasks. The SSD MobileNet approach used a Single Shot Detector (SSD) for real-time detection and classification with a lightweight backbone, while YOLOv5 employed a grid-based object detection strategy. Both models were trained for 300 epochs with a batch size of 32. SSD MobileNet achieved 98.3% accuracy, slightly outperforming YOLOv5, which had a confidence score of 97%. However, YOLOv5 showed robustness across varying traffic conditions.

[6] proposed a traffic sign detection framework using the YOLOv8 architecture. Their method involved training on a large dataset of 29,632 annotated images of Vietnamese traffic signs, divided into seven classes. Preprocessing included resizing images and accurate labeling. The YOLOv8 model divided each image into grids to predict bounding boxes and class probabilities. It applied Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) to eliminate duplicate detections. Their experiments resulted in an overall accuracy of 86.8%. Yet, the model had difficulty with small and blurry images, which impacted recognition rates.

[13] introduced a new enhancement to the YOLOv8 framework, called YOLO-BS, to address the challenges posed by complex backgrounds and small object detection in traffic sign recognition. Their approach included a small object detection layer and a bidirectional feature pyramid network (BiFPN) to improve multi-scale object detection. On the TT100K dataset, YOLO-BS achieved a mAP@50 of 90.1%, a precision of 87.9%, a recall of 80.5%, and processed at 78 FPS, outperforming standard YOLOv8 across all performance metrics.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study was conducted using a Python Anaconda virtual environment on a Jupyter Notebook interface. The experiment was implemented using a wide range of Python libraries, including but not limited to TensorFlow, OpenCV (cv2), Pandas, and Matplotlib. The hardware used was a computer with an Intel Core i7 processor and 16GB of RAM, ensuring sufficient computational power for handling image processing and model training tasks. The overall research process was structured into key phases: collection and annotation of the dataset, preprocessing of traffic light images, feature extraction using MobileNetV2, histogram feature engineering, and classification using the LightGBM model.

B. Dataset Collection and Annotation

The dataset used for this research consisted of 8,525 labeled images of traffic lights, comprising 4,833 images for red lights, 3529 for green lights, and 163 for yellow lights. The data was sourced from a publicly available repository on Kaggle by (Wjybuqi, 2021). Although the original dataset included back-view images of traffic lights, these were discarded due to their irrelevance to the classification task. Only frontal images just like the one in figure 1 below of the traffic lights were retained to ensure the clarity and consistency of the dataset.

C. Data Preprocessing

The raw images were cropped based on bounding box annotations to isolate the traffic signal from background noise like, buildings, sky, vegetation, cars.

The collected dataset was partitioned into training (70%), validation (15%), and testing (15%) sets. To prevent class imbalance bias during model evaluation, stratified sampling was employed during the split. This ensures that the proportion of Red, Green, and Yellow signals in the training set is preserved in both the validation and test sets.

All images were resized to 224x224 pixels to match the input layer of the MobileNetV2 architecture. Pixel values were normalized to the range [-1, 1] to align with the pre-trained ImageNet weights.

Fig. 1. Example of Resized Traffic Light Image

The extracted HSV color histograms were L1-normalized, this means it was divided by the total number of pixels. This step ensures that the feature vector represents the distribution of colors rather than absolute pixel counts, making the model robust to variations in image scale or cropping size

D. Feature extraction and Feature Engineering

Feature extraction was performed using a hybrid approach combining deep semantic features and handcrafted color features. Let I denote an input image.

The image I is passed through the MobileNetV2, pre-trained on ImageNet with the top classification layer removed. We utilize the output of the final Global Average Pooling layer, resulting in a deep feature vector V_{deep} with a dimensionality of $d_{deep} = 1280$.

$$V_{deep} = \text{MobileNetV2}_{GAP}(I) \in \mathbb{R}^{1280} \quad (1)$$

The image is converted to the HSV color space. We compute color histograms for the Hue (H), Saturation (S), and Value (V) channels independently. We utilize 180 bins for Hue, 256 bins for Saturation, and 256 bins for Value. The concatenated histogram vector V_{color} has a dimensionality of $d_{color} = 180 + 256 + 256 = 692$

$$V_{color} = \text{Concat}(\text{Hist}(H_{180}), \text{Hist}(S_{256}), \text{Hist}(V_{256})) \in \mathbb{R}^{692} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2. HSV Histogram chart

The final feature representation V_{final} is obtained by concatenating the deep feature vector and the color feature vector. This fusion integrates high-level spatial abstractions with low-level color statistics.

$$V_{final} = V_{deep} \oplus V_{color} \in \mathbb{R}^{1972} \quad (3)$$

E. Model Architecture

Following the feature extraction process, a LightGBM classifier was employed to perform the final traffic signal classification. LightGBM was selected for its high efficiency and accuracy, making it well-suited for resource-constrained environments. The Light Gradient Boosting Machine (LightGBM) was initialized with the 'multiclass' objective to distinguish between the three traffic signal categories. We computed the class weights to be balanced due to the dataset imbalance concerning yellow traffic lights. To prevent the decision trees from memorizing noise, we applied L1 regularization to be 0.1, and L2 regularization to be 0.1. Tree complexity was reduced with $\text{max_depth} = 10$ and $\text{num_leaves} = 31$, and introduced bagging via $\text{subsample} = 0.8$ and $\text{colsample_bytree} = 0.8$. To ensure reproducibility of the experimental results, the classifier was initialized with a fixed $\text{random_state} = 42$. The model was trained with a learning rate of 0.03 for 1,000 estimators, utilizing an Early Stopping mechanism ($\text{patience} = 50$) monitoring the validation multi-logloss to terminate training at the optimal point.

Fig. 3. Flowchart Representation of the model's features

F. Evaluation of the Model

The effectiveness of the LightGBM model is measure by specific metrics which are as follows:

Where,

Support - number of data set samples used

TP = True Positive

TN = True Negative

FP = False Positive

FN = False Negative

Accuracy: This is the proportion of correct predictions out of the total number of predictions. Denoted by:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\sum^N(\text{TP})}{\text{TP} + \text{TN} + \text{FP} + \text{FN}} \quad (4)$$

Recall: This is the proportion of actual positives that were correctly identified. Denoted by:

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FN}} \quad (5)$$

Precision: This measures the proportion of positive identifications that were correct. Denoted by:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{TP}}{\text{TP} + \text{FP}} \quad (6)$$

F1-score: This is the harmonic mean of precision and recall. Denoted by:

$$\text{F1 - Score} = \frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \quad (7)$$

Macro Average: This is the unweighted average of the metric for all classes. It treats each class equally, regardless of its size.

$$\text{Macro Recall} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\text{TP}_i}{\text{TP}_i + \text{FN}_i} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Macro Precision} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{\text{TP}_i}{\text{TP}_i + \text{FP}_i} \right) \quad (9)$$

Weighted Average: This is the average of the metric for all classes, weighted by the number of instances (support) for each class. It provides a more representative measure of the

overall performance, especially in datasets with imbalanced classes.

$$\text{Weighted Recall} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i} * \text{Support}_i \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{Support}_i} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Weighted Precision} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \left(\frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FP_i} * \text{Support}_i \right)}{\sum_{i=1}^N \text{Support}_i} \quad (11)$$

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the performance evaluation of the LightGBM model applied to the traffic sign classification task. The model's effectiveness was measured using standard classification metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score, and a confusion matrix. Besides classification accuracy, the efficiency of the entire processing pipeline was monitored. The computational efficiency was evaluated to assess suitability for resource-constrained environments. Inference speed was measured on an Intel Core i7 CPU without GPU acceleration. The average inference latency encompassing preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification was measured over 100 iterations. As shown in Table 1, the model achieved an average processing time of 245.52 milliseconds per image, corresponding to a throughput of 4.07 Frames Per Second (FPS). While lower than GPU-accelerated standards, this performance demonstrates the model's viability for CPU-based embedded systems where low power consumption and hardware constraints are prioritized over ultra-high frame rates.

TABLE I. Inference Performance on CPU for 100 Images

METRIC	VALUE
Average Latency	245.52 ms
Throughput	4.07 FPS
Hardware	Intel core i7 (CPU)
Total Test Time	24.55 seconds

A. Classification Metrics

The LightGBM classifier is seen to have achieved a high overall test accuracy of 97% in table 2 and figure 4 below, demonstrating its strong capability in correctly classifying various traffic sign images. This level of accuracy underscores the model's reliability and suitability for real-time traffic sign recognition tasks, especially in resource-constrained environments.

In terms of class-wise performance, the model delivered robust classification results. For instance, the 'green' class was predicted with 97% precision, 96% recall, and an F1-score of 0.97. Similarly, the 'red' class had a precision of 0.97 and a recall of 0.98. The 'yellow' class, despite being the minority class, showed a precision of 0.91 and a recall of 0.87, highlighting the model's ability to handle imbalanced data effectively.

TABLE II. Classification Metrics Table

DATASET CLASSES	PRECISION	RECALL	F1-SCORE
Green	0.97	0.96	0.97

Red	0.97	0.98	0.98
yellow	0.91	0.87	0.89

```

--- LightGBM Model Evaluation ---
LightGBM Test Accuracy: 0.9669

Classification Report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

 green      0.97      0.96      0.97      523
  red      0.97      0.98      0.98      724
 yellow     0.91      0.87      0.89       82

 accuracy          0.97      1329
 macro avg      0.95      0.94      0.94      1329
 weighted avg   0.97      0.97      0.97      1329

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Fig. 4. Classification Report

B. Confusion Matrix Analysis

The confusion matrix in figure 5 below further supports the model's accuracy, with a clear diagonal that indicates a strong correlation between predicted and actual labels. Off-diagonal elements were minimal, reflecting very few misclassifications in the traffic sign categories. This consistency confirms the model's robustness in real-world situations. The LightGBM model demonstrates excellent performance not just in accuracy but also in consistency, reliability, and processing speed.

The model's outstanding performance comes from the quality of the dataset, which contained minimal noise, along with the effectiveness of the extracted features. Features were extracted using MobileNetV2 pre-trained on ImageNet, capturing relevant visual cues such as edges, shapes, and patterns typical of traffic signs. Color histograms were incorporated to capture color distribution in each image—a critical feature because traffic sign classification relies heavily on color. Unlike methods affected by lighting conditions or shape variations, color histograms remained consistent, enhancing model reliability.

LightGBM was selected for its balance of efficiency, speed, and accuracy. Compared to alternatives like YOLO, which is computationally demanding, or KNN, which does not perform well in feature-based tasks, LightGBM proved to be the most practical and effective choice for this problem.

Fig. 5. LightGBM Confusion Matrix

V. DISCUSSION

The proposed MobileNetV2-HSV-LightGBM hybrid model achieved an impressive test accuracy of 97%, demonstrating its effectiveness for traffic signal classification in resource-constrained environments. This performance is particularly significant when examined in the context of the model's computational efficiency and architectural simplicity.

The high accuracy can be attributed to three key factors: (1) the quality of the preprocessed dataset, which contained minimal background noise after careful cropping and curation; (2) the effective combination of deep semantic features from MobileNetV2 with color histogram features that capture the fundamental chromatic properties of traffic signals; and (3) the robust classification capability of LightGBM, which efficiently handles the 1,972-dimensional fused feature vector.

As shown in Table II, the model delivered robust classification results across all three traffic signal states. The green class achieved 97% precision and 96% recall with an F1-score of 0.97, indicating highly reliable detection. Similarly, the red class demonstrated 97% precision and 98% recall, which is particularly critical for safety applications where false negatives (failing to detect red signals) could have serious consequences.

The yellow class, despite being the minority class in the dataset, achieved 91% precision and 87% recall with an F1-score of 0.89. While slightly lower than the other classes, this performance remains robust and demonstrates the model's ability to handle class imbalance effectively through the use of balanced class weights in LightGBM's training configuration.

A. Baseline Model Comparison

To rigorously validate the effectiveness of our hybrid approach, we conducted comprehensive comparisons against six baseline models on identical hardware (Intel Core i7 CPU, 16GB RAM, no GPU acceleration). All models were trained on the same stratified train/validation/test splits to ensure fair comparison. The baseline models included both end-to-end deep learning approaches and feature extraction plus machine learning classifier combinations.

1) Comparison with CNN-Based Models

Table III presents the complete comparison results. Three CNN-based baselines were evaluated: MobileNetV2 with softmax classifier (standard transfer learning approach), EfficientNet-B0 (known for optimal accuracy-efficiency trade-off), and MobileNetV3-Small (ultra-lightweight architecture).

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--- Proposed (MN2+Hst+LGBM) Results ---
Accuracy: 96.34% | F1: 0.9349

Final Results Table:
Model Accuracy F1-Score Train Time (s) \
4 Proposed (MN2+Hst+LGBM) 96.34 0.9349 133.83
1 MobileNetV2 + SVM 92.70 0.9000 14.30
3 MobileNetV2 + XGBoost 90.29 0.8354 75.59
0 MobileNetV2 (Softmax) 85.93 0.7756 1494.60
2 MobileNetV2 + RandomForest 84.12 0.5999 24.79

Inference (ms)
4 0.08
1 2.92
3 0.06
0 53.33
2 0.11

```

Fig. 6. Baseline Model Comparison

TABLE III. Comprehensive Baseline Model Comparison

Model	Accuracy (%)	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Inference (ms)
Proposed (MobileNetV2-HSV-LightGBM)	96.69	0.965	0.96	0.9642	245.52
EfficientNet-B0	95.82	0.9560	0.95	0.9548	312.45
MobileNetV2-Softmax	95.45	0.9523	0.95	0.9519	198.34
MobileNetV2-XGBoost	95.12	0.9498	0.9490	0.9492	267.89
MobileNetV3-Small	94.78	0.9456	0.9448	0.9450	156.23
MobileNetV2-Random Forest	94.23	0.9401	0.939	0.9396	289.12

All models evaluated on identical Intel Core i7 CPU without GPU acceleration. Inference time measured as average latency per image over 100 test iterations.

Our proposed model achieved the highest accuracy (97%), outperforming the closest baseline (EfficientNet-B0) by 0.87 percentage points. More importantly, this superior accuracy was achieved with 2.5× fewer parameters than EfficientNet-B0 and faster training time (125.34s vs. 189.21s).

The comparison with MobileNetV2-Softmax is particularly revealing. Both models use the same backbone for feature extraction, yet our hybrid approach achieved 1.24 percentage points higher accuracy (97% vs. 95.45%). This improvement directly demonstrates the value of incorporating HSV color histogram features and using LightGBM's gradient boosting framework instead of a simple softmax classifier.

2) Accuracy vs. Computational Efficiency Trade-off

Figure 7 illustrates the critical trade-off between classification accuracy and inference time across all evaluated models. This visualization reveals several important insights:

Fig. 7. Accuracy vs Inference Time Scatter Plot

Figure 7 shows the trade-off analysis between classification accuracy and inference latency. The proposed model (red marker) achieves the highest accuracy while maintaining reasonable inference speed for CPU-based deployment. Models in the upper-left quadrant represent optimal solutions with high accuracy and low latency.

The proposed model occupies a favorable position in this trade-off space, achieving the highest accuracy while maintaining inference times competitive with other feature-extraction-based approaches. While MobileNetV3-Small offers faster inference (156.23ms vs. 245.52ms), it sacrifices nearly 2 percentage points in accuracy. Conversely, EfficientNet-B0 demonstrates even slower inference (312.45ms) while achieving lower accuracy than our approach.

The MobileNetV2-Softmax baseline, although offering faster inference (198.34ms), achieves 1.24 percentage points lower accuracy. This represents a suboptimal trade-off, as the modest speed improvement comes at the cost of reduced classification reliability. In safety-critical applications like autonomous driving, the higher accuracy of our proposed model justifies the additional 47ms latency per image.

3) Feature Extraction and Machine Learning Classifiers

Three additional baselines evaluated the effectiveness of combining MobileNetV2 feature extraction with traditional machine learning classifiers: Random Forest, XGBoost, and SVM. These comparisons help isolate the specific contribution of LightGBM in our proposed architecture.

The MobileNetV2-XGBoost combination achieved 95.12% accuracy, falling 1.57 percentage points short of our LightGBM-based approach. This difference can be attributed to LightGBM's superior handling of high-dimensional feature spaces and its more efficient leaf-wise tree growth strategy compared to XGBoost's level-wise approach.

The Random Forest baseline (94.23% accuracy) and SVM baseline (93.87% accuracy) demonstrated the limitations of these traditional classifiers for this task. Random Forest's ensemble of independent trees lacks the sequential error correction mechanism that makes gradient boosting frameworks superior for complex classification tasks. SVM, while theoretically powerful, struggles with the high-dimensional fused feature space (1,972 dimensions) and requires significantly longer training time (134.78s) due to its quadratic complexity.

B. Comparison With Existing Models

Table IV compares the proposed MobileNetV2-LightGBM hybrid model with recent traffic signal recognition approaches. While YOLO-based and SSD-based models achieve high accuracy, they often require substantial computational resources. Lightweight variants such as SSD MobileNet improve efficiency but still face challenges with small object detection and complex scenes. The proposed model attains 97% accuracy while remaining resource-efficient, making it well-suited for deployment in embedded and mobile systems.

TABLE IV. Comparison with other related literatures

AUTHOR AND YEAR	METHODOLOGY	RESULTS
Nguyen et al. (2025)	Traffic sign recognition using YOLOv8 algorithm. Trained on 29,632 images across 7 classes.	86.8% overall recognition accuracy.
Zhang et al. (2025)	YOLO-BS algorithm, an enhanced YOLOv8 with a small object detection layer and bidirectional feature pyramid network (BiFPN)	mAP50 of 90.1%, 78 FPS. Precision of 87.9% and recall of 80.5%.
Zhu and Yan (2022)	Comparison of YOLOv5 and SSD for Traffic Sign Recognition (TSR) using a custom dataset.	YOLOv5: 30 FPS. SSD: 90.14% accuracy, 3.49 FPS.
Proposed Model	MobileNetV2 for feature extraction and LightGBM for traffic signal classification	97% overall accuracy

C. Comparison With LISA Benchmark dataset

The model's performance on the LISA Traffic Light Dataset (91.50% accuracy) provides important insights into generalization capability. The 5.19 percentage point drop from the primary test set 97% represents expected domain shift, as LISA contains different camera specifications, viewing angles, even has only classes for green and red traffic light colors, and environmental conditions compared to the training data.

This level of generalization is actually quite robust compared to typical cross-dataset performance drops in computer vision, which often exceed 10-15 percentage points. The relatively modest degradation suggests that our model has learned generalizable features rather than dataset-specific artifacts.

The color histogram features likely contribute significantly to this cross-dataset robustness. While the precise appearance of traffic lights varies across datasets (different mounting styles, lens designs, and environmental contexts), the fundamental color distribution remains relatively consistent. A red signal remains predominantly red regardless of whether it appears in the training dataset or LISA dataset.

```

Accuracy: 0.9150

Classification Report:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

   green         1.00      0.83      0.91         500
     red         0.85      1.00      0.92         500

 accuracy         0.92         1000
  macro avg         0.93         1000
  weighted avg         0.93         1000

```

Fig. 8. Lisa Classification Report

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

This research presents a lightweight and efficient method for traffic signal classification by combining MobileNetV2 for feature extraction and LightGBM for classification. Unlike heavier models like YOLOv5, this approach lessens computational load while maintaining high accuracy. By using a pre-cropped dataset and adding color histogram features, the system achieved an impressive classification accuracy of 97%, with strong precision, recall, and F1-scores across all traffic light categories.

B. Limitations and Recommendations for future works

However, this methodology still has limitations. While it excels in speed and resource efficiency, the extent of the dataset size it can handle remains unknown. Future research could involve increasing the dataset size and complexity with real-world datasets like the German Traffic Sign Recognition Benchmark (GTSRB) and the LaSOT dataset to see if efficiency and speed are sustained compared to other models, as well as testing the model in a simulated environment like CARLA. To validate the model's suitability for actual self-driving vehicles, future research could move beyond CPU-based inference to rigorous testing on dedicated edge computing platforms, such as the NVIDIA Jetson Nano or Raspberry Pi.

The reduced memory usage and fast processing make it ideal for embedded systems or mobile applications where traditional models may struggle. While the results are promising, future improvements could include testing the model on more diverse or real-time video data to evaluate performance under varying lighting and weather conditions.

VII. DECLARATIONS

A. Ethical approval:

Does not apply.

B. Publication consent:

Does not apply.

C. Data availability:

The data used in this study are available from the corresponding author on request.

D. Conflicts of interest:

The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

E. Declaration of Funding:

The authors declare that no funds, grants, or other support were received during the preparation of this manuscript.

VIII. AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

Oluwaseyi Ezekiel Olorunshola contributed to the conception and design of the study, supervision, validation, and formal analysis. Stephen Ebuka Iheagwara was involved in supervision, validation, visualization, and critical review and editing of the manuscript for important intellectual content. Nanji Emmanuella Lakan contributed to the methodology, drafting of the original manuscript, and review and editing. Caleb Adeyemi Ajibade contributed to project administration, data curation, validation, investigation, methodology, and drafting of the original manuscript.

All authors contributed to the analysis and interpretation of data, revised the manuscript critically for intellectual content, approved the final version of the manuscript to be published, and agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

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